

Further studies on the transformation of withasteroids on solid surface

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Withasteroids have been found to undergo a variety of chemical transformations on a bed of alumina at ambient as well as elevated temperature. Some interesting transformations are reported here.

In a previous communication¹, we reported the opening of oxide rings of appropriately functionalised withasteroids on a bed of neutral alumina. We extended our investigation on the transformation of withasteroids on solid surface and observed that not merely opening but also formation of oxide rings may take place under proper condition, if the substituents on withasteroids are suitable for such transformation. Thus, when a methanolic solution of the chlorine-containing withanolide², physalolactone (**1**) was adsorbed on a bed of alumina and left at ambient temperature for 72 h, the major product was characterised as **2**, the methanol adduct of 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E³. Obviously, the *trans*-diequatorial chlorohydrin grouping of **1** was first converted to an epoxide to give 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E which then yielded the Michael addition product of methanol¹.

Again, when withafastuosin E (**3**), a withanolide of *Datura fastuosa*⁴, was adsorbed on chromatographic grade

bicyclic side-chain with an allyl ether bridge. The formation of **4** obviously takes place by elimination of a molecule of water from **3** by S_N2 type reaction.

When a methanolic solution of withanolide E (**5**) was adsorbed on a bed of acid-washed alumina and left for 72 h at ambient temperature prior to desorption with methanol, a complex mixture, almost free from the starting material, was obtained. Chromatographic resolution of this mixture over silica gel yielded four different compounds which were identified as withanolide S (**6**), 14-dehydrowithanolide S (**7**), 5-*O*-methyl ether of 14-dehydrowithanolide S (**8**) and a cyclic oxide (**9**) which was recognised to be the methyl ether of a 14,20-oxide earlier reported^{6,7} to be formed by treatment of withanolide E (**5**) with acetone-H₂SO₄ and later prepared by us by treatment with KHSO₄-dioxane⁸.

While withanolide S (**6**) was identified by direct com-

alumina or silica gel and then heated in an oven at 110° for 6 h, the major product was withametelin G (**4**), a withanolide of the flowers of *Datura metel*⁵ which bears a

parison with authentic sample, its 14-dehydro derivative (**7**) was characterised by ¹H nmr and mass spectral comparison with the former. The molecular ion peak of **7** (M⁺,

m/z 486) was 18 m.u. less than that of **6** and it showed an extra olefinic hydrogen signal at δ 5.16 and two extra *sp*² carbon signals at δ 113.9 and 150.6, respectively, in its ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectrum. The methyl ether (**8**) showed MH⁺ peak at *m/z* 501 in its FAB mass spectrum and an ¹H nmr spectrum same as that of **7** with the lone exception of a high field methoxy signal at δ 2.93. This chemical shift of the methoxy signal is suggestive of its attachment to C-5 rather than to C-6 and this was confirmed by preparation of its monoacetate which showed a low field carbonyl hydrogen (H-6) signal at δ 5.15 overlapping the signal for olefinic hydrogen at C-15.

Compound **9** is isomeric with **8** and it also showed a high field methoxy signal at δ 2.98 but no olefinic hydrogen or *sp*² carbon signal other than those present in the parent molecule was discernible in its ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra. It was, therefore, surmised that **9** was formed by elimination of a molecule of water from two hydroxyl groups or in other words, the molecule bears an oxide linkage. Acid-catalysed transformation of withanolide E (**5**) to a 14,20-oxide **9** (R = H) is well recorded⁶ and our compound was proved to be its 5-*O*-methyl ether.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. ¹H (400 MHz) and ¹³C (100 MHz) nmr spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ unless otherwise stated. Aluminium oxide Active Neutral (Qualigens) was used. For preparation of acid washed alumina, neutral alumina was kept submerged in 1 *N* methanolic HCl for 0.5 h and then filtered, washed free from chloride ions and dried in air. Silica gel 70–325 mesh (Centron Research Laboratories) and silica gel G (Qualigens) were used for cc and tlc respectively.

Conversion of physalolactone (1) to 2: A solution of physalolactone (0.1 g) in MeOH containing a few drops of CHCl₃ was adsorbed on a small bed of neutral alumina (7 g) and left at ambient temperature for 72 h. The adsorbed material was then washed down with MeOH. The residue from MeOH washings showed two distinct tlc spots in addition to a major spot for the unreacted material. Separation of the reaction products yielded a chlorine-free compound (17 mg, m.p. 183°) and an amorphous chlorine containing compound (6 mg). The chlorine-free compound (MH⁺, *m/z* 535) was indistinguishable (m.m.p., co-tlc, ¹H nmr) from the methanol adduct of 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E (**2**), earlier prepared³ by treatment of a methanolic solution of 4 β -hydroxywithanolide E with 1 *N* methanolic KOH.

Conversion of withafatuosin E (3) to withametelin G (4): A methanolic solution of withafatuosin E (0.1 g) was poured slowly with stirring on alumina or silica gel (5 g) taken in a small basin. Stirring was continued till the adsorbent became free-flowing again when it was kept in an

oven maintained at 110° for 6 h. The adsorbent was brought to room temperature and leached with EtOAc. Removal of the solvent yielded a near-homogeneous solid (30 mg) which was purified by passing it through a short bed of silica gel and eluting it with hexane-EtOAc (1 : 10) to yield an amorphous powder (M⁺, *m/z* 470) which was found to be identical with withametelin G (**4**) by direct comparison (co-tlc, ¹H nmr, ms).

Conversion of withanolide E (5) to 6, 7, 8 and 9: A methanolic solution of withanolide E (0.15 g) was adsorbed on a small bed of acid-washed alumina (7 g) and left at ambient temperature for 72 h. The adsorbed material was then washed down with MeOH and the residue obtained by removal of solvent was chromatographed over a bed of silica gel. Elution with C₆H₆-EtOAc (3 : 1) yielded a solid (30 mg) which was crystallised from EtOAc to give needles of **8**, m.p. 275–78°; ¹H nmr δ (CD₃OD) 6.56 (1H, ddd, *J* 10.1, 5.4, 2.1 Hz, H-3), 5.64 (1H, dd, *J* 10.1, 2.6 Hz, H-2), 5.06 (1H, br s, H-15), 4.57 (1H, dd, *J* 13.3, 3.2 Hz, H-22), 3.86 (1H, br t, *J* 2.7 Hz, H-6), 2.93 (3H, s, OMe), 1.92 (3H, s, Me-28), 1.77 (3H, s, Me-27), 1.26 (3H, s, Me-19), 1.23 (3H, s, Me-21), 1.1 (3H, s, Me-18).

Later fractions of C₆H₆-EtOAc (3 : 1) eluate yielded an amorphous solid (10 mg) which was crystallised from hexane-EtOAc mixture to yield crystals of **7**, m.p. 210–15°, ¹H nmr δ 6.59 (1H, ddd, *J* 10, 4.8, 2.4 Hz, H-3), 5.86 (1H, dd, *J* 10, 2.4 Hz, H-2), 5.16 (1H, br s, H-15), 4.65 (1H, dd, *J* 12.4, 3.6 Hz, H-22), 3.74 (1H, narrow t, H-6), 3.30 (1H, dt, *J* 19.8, 2.4 Hz, 4 β -H), 1.20, 1.30, 1.34, 1.86, 1.94 (3H, s each, Me-18, 19, 21, 27, 28); ¹³C nmr δ (C-1 to C-28) 203.8, 128.7, 141.2, 35.9, 77.5, 74.5, 29.5, 32.8, 43.9, 23.9, 41.7, 56.5, 150.6, 113.9, 35.8, 87.0, 17.7, 15.5, 77.4, 20.4, 80.2, 31.5, 152.9, 128.7, 167.5, 12.3, 20.6.

Elution of the column with C₆H₆-EtOAc (1 : 1) yielded **9** as a homogeneous amorphous solid (57 mg), m.p. 271–75°; FABMS : MH⁺ *m/z* 501; ¹H nmr δ 6.41 (1H, ddd, *J* 10, 5.2, 2.8 Hz, H-3), 5.78 (1H, dd, *J* 10, 2.8 Hz, H-2), 4.91 (1H, br dd, H-22), 3.96 (1H, br s, H-6), 3.07 (3H, s, OMe), 1.18, 1.28, 1.39, 1.86, 1.91 (3H, s each, Me-18, 19, 21, 27, 28); ¹³C nmr (C-1 to C-28) 205.1, 129.1, 139.7, 37.5, 81.6, 68.7, 27.6, 33.8, 34.3, 52.8, 22.6, 29.4, 49.7, 87.9, 32.4, 33.7, 83.2, 19.6, 15.6, 78.9, 26.9, 80.7, 30.8, 151.3, 121.1, 166.8, 12.3, 20.6, 54.8 (OMe).

Elution with EtOAc-MeOH (9 : 1) yielded a colourless solid (7 mg) which was identified as withanolide S (**6**) by direct comparison with authentic sample (ms, co-tlc, ¹H nmr).

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Note

References

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